

Efficacy and Tolerability of Vagus Nerve Stimulation Therapy (VNS) in Epileptic Patients at Baghdad Teaching Hospital

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Abstract

Background: Vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) is an established adjuvant therapy for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy (DRE) who are not candidates for resective epilepsy surgery. It has been increasingly used in both pediatric and adult populations to reduce seizure burden and improve quality of life. This study reviews the experience with VNS therapy for DRE at Baghdad Teaching Hospital. **Patients and Methods:** This uncontrolled retrospective study was conducted at the epilepsy clinic of Baghdad Teaching Hospital. Medical records of 71 patients with DRE who underwent VNS implantation between 2015 and January 2023 were reviewed. The cohort included 51 males and 20 females. Collected variables comprised age at implantation, sex, age at seizure onset, duration of follow-up, seizure type, seizure frequency before and after implantation, epilepsy etiology (lesional or non-lesional), VNS stimulation parameters at the last follow-up visit, and reported adverse effects. Data were analyzed descriptively to assess clinical outcomes and tolerability. **Results:** The age of epilepsy onset was <1 year in 27 patients (38.0%), 1–10 years in 34 patients (47.9%), and >10 years in 10 patients (14.1%). Seizure types included focal seizures in 13 patients (18.3%), generalized seizures in 10 (14.1%), focal to bilateral tonic-clonic seizures in 20 (28.2%), and multiple seizure types in 28 (39.4%). Overall, 56 patients (78.9%) showed a clinical response to VNS therapy, while 15 (21.1%) were non-responders. Adverse effects were reported in 30 patients (42.3%), with hoarseness of voice being the most common (32.4%), followed by shortness of breath (15.5%). Most side effects were mild and manageable. **Conclusion:** VNS is a safe, tolerable, and effective adjuvant treatment for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy who are not suitable candidates for surgical intervention. Seizure control tends to improve over time after implantation, and the majority of adverse effects are mild and well tolerated.

Introduction

An epileptic seizure is defined by the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) as a transient occurrence of signs and/or symptoms resulting from abnormal, excessive, or synchronous neuronal activity in the brain [1]. Epilepsy, in turn, is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by an enduring predisposition to generate epileptic seizures, along with associated neurobiological, cognitive, psychological, and social consequences [1]. In 2014, the ILAE introduced a practical clinical definition of epilepsy

to better reflect real-world practice, defining epilepsy as the occurrence of at least two unprovoked seizures more than 24 hours apart, a single unprovoked seizure with a high probability ($\geq 60\%$) of recurrence over the subsequent 10 years, or the diagnosis of a specific epilepsy syndrome [2]. Despite advances in diagnosis and management, epilepsy remains a major global health problem. Drug-resistant epilepsy (DRE) is defined as the failure of adequate trials of two appropriately chosen and well-tolerated antiepileptic drug regimens, whether used as monotherapy or in

More Information

How to cite this article: Taib AH, Yousif OO, Jaddoa AG. Efficacy and Tolerability of Vagus Nerve Stimulation Therapy (VNS) in Epileptic Patients at Baghdad Teaching Hospital. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2026;4(1):105-10.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).15

Keywords:

Vagus nerve stimulation, drug-resistant epilepsy, neuromodulation, seizure control, adverse effects.

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combination, to achieve sustained seizure freedom for at least one year or three times the longest pre-treatment inter-seizure interval [3]. Approximately one-third of individuals with epilepsy develop DRE, making it a particularly challenging subgroup to manage [4]. Patients with epilepsy, especially those with DRE, experience significantly impaired quality of life, disrupted family and social functioning, and reduced psychosocial well-being compared with individuals suffering from other chronic illnesses [3,4]. Moreover, DRE is associated with an increased risk of morbidity, mortality, and sudden unexpected death in epilepsy (SUDEP) [5]. The lifetime risk of experiencing at least one seizure is approximately 5–10%, with peak incidence occurring in early childhood and late adulthood [6]. Globally, epilepsy affects an estimated 50 million people, with nearly 85% living in developing countries [7]. Epilepsy accounts for a substantial proportion of the global burden of neurological disease, contributing millions of disability-adjusted life years, particularly in low- and middle-income regions where access to specialized care is limited [5,8]. While anti-seizure medications remain the cornerstone of epilepsy management, their effectiveness is limited in a significant proportion of patients, and long-term use may be associated with adverse effects, toxicity, and poor adherence [9,10]. Surgical treatment offers the best chance of seizure freedom in selected patients; however, many individuals with DRE are not suitable surgical candidates. Consequently, alternative non-pharmacological therapies have gained importance. Vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) has emerged as an effective and well-tolerated adjunctive treatment for patients with DRE who are not candidates for respective surgery, offering meaningful seizure reduction and improved long-term outcomes [11]. The present study aims to evaluate the efficacy and tolerability of VNS therapy in patients with drug-resistant epilepsy treated at the epilepsy clinic of Baghdad Teaching Hospital, and to provide insight into optimizing long-term follow-up and management strategies in this population.

Method

This study was designed as a retrospective observational analysis evaluating the efficacy and tolerability of vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) therapy in patients with drug-resistant epilepsy during the follow-up period from implantation until the last documented clinic visit in January 2023. The study was conducted at the epilepsy clinic of Baghdad Teaching Hospital. Medical records of 71 patients diagnosed with drug-resistant epilepsy were reviewed. All diagnoses were established by neurologists specialized in epilepsy according to accepted clinical criteria. The cohort included patients who underwent VNS implantation between January 2015 and January 2023; however,

four patients had been implanted earlier in 2014 and were also included due to continued follow-up at the clinic. All implantations were performed by neurosurgeons trained and supervised by an official product manager to ensure standardized surgical technique. Data extracted from patients’ medical files included sex, age at the time of VNS implantation (years), age at seizure onset, epilepsy etiology, seizure type, seizure frequency before VNS implantation, seizure frequency after implantation, duration of follow-up, stimulation output current at the last visit, and reported adverse effects. Epilepsy etiology was categorized as lesional or non-lesional based on neuroimaging findings. Seizure types were classified into focal, generalized, focal to bilateral tonic-clonic, or multiple seizure types. VNS devices were implanted under general anesthesia using a two-incision technique. Generator models 100 and 101 were used in all patients. Intraoperative lead impedance testing was performed using standardized procedures to confirm system integrity. Stimulation was initiated two weeks after implantation, starting with an output current of 0.25 mA. The current was gradually increased every 1–2 weeks according to clinical response and tolerability. Standard stimulation parameters included a signal frequency of 20–30 Hz, pulse width of 250–500 μs, an on-time of 30 seconds, and an off-time of 5 minutes. These parameters were adjusted individually based on seizure control and side-effect profile.

Results

A total of 71 patients were enrolled in the current study, more than two-thirds of the patients (71.8%) were male. As shown in table 1.

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution of the Patients

Sociodemographic characteristics		N (%)
Age group (years)	<10	27 (38.0)
	10-19	17 (23.9)
	20-29	14 (19.7)
	≥30	13 (18.3)
Gender	Male	51 (71.8)
	Female	20 (28.2)

About 38% of the patients had the first attack of seizure at the age of < 1 year, 47.9% of them at the age of 1-10 years. The focal seizure was presented in 18.3 patients, generalized seizure in 14.1%, while focal to bilateral tonic-clonic seizure was presented in 28.2%. More than half of the patients (53.5%) had lesional disorders. As shown in table 2.

Table 2: Characteristics of Seizure

Characteristics of seizure		N (%)
Age at onset	< 1 year	27 (38.0)
	1-10 years	34 (47.9)
	>10 years	10 (14.1)

Types of seizure	Focal	13 (18.3)
	Generalized	10 (14.1)
	Focal to bilateral tonic-clonic	20 (28.2)
	Multiple types	28 (39.4)
Diagnosis	Lesional	38 (53.5)
	Non-lesional	33 (46.5)
Frequency /month	<20	41 (57.7)
	20-39	12 (16.9)
	40-59	3 (4.2)
	60-79	7 (9.9)
	80-100	1 (1.4)
	>100	7 (9.9)

Regarding the treatment, 25.4% of the patients were treated for ≤6 months, 47.9% were treated for 7-12 months, 21.1% were treated for 13-24 months, and 5.6% were treated for >24 months (Table 3).

The response rate was 78.9%, while 21.1% of the patients did not respond to the treatment as shown in figure 1.

The percentage of patients with seizure frequency of > 100 attacks/month significantly decreased after treatment (P-value=0.028), while the percentage of those with a frequency of < 20 attacks/month significantly increased (P- value=0.020), as shown in table 4.

Figure 1: Response Rate of the Treatment

Table 3: Characteristics of Treatment

Characteristics of treatment		N (%)
Duration of implantation	≤6 months	18 (25.4)
	7-12 months	34 (47.9)
	13-24 Onths	15 (21.1)
	>24 months	4 (5.6)
Pulse width	250 μs	27 (38.0)
	500 μs	44 (62.0)
Signal frequency	20 Hz	6 (8.5)
	25 Hz	4 (5.6)
	30 Hz	61 (85.9)
Current output	<1 mA (0.25, 0.75)	9 (12.7)
	1-<2 mA (1, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75)	13 (18.3)
	2-<3 mA (2, 2.25, 2.5, 2.75)	35 (49.3)
	≥3 (3,3.25)	14 (19.7)

Table 4: Trend of the Seizure Frequency after Treatment

Seizure frequency/month	Before intervention	After intervention	P-value
<20	41 (57.7)	54 (76.1)	0.020
20-39	12 (16.9)	10 (14.1)	0.646
40-59	3 (4.2)	1 (1.4)	0.313
60-79	7 (9.9)	4 (5.6)	0.339
80-100	1 (1.4)	1 (1.4)	1
>100	7 (9.9)	1 (1.4)	0.028

There was no significant association between the response rate and the age and sex of the patients as shown in table 5.

No significant association was obtained between the response rate and age at the first onset, type of seizure, diagnosis, and frequency/ month (Table 6).

There was no significant association between the response rate and duration of the treatment, pulse width, signal frequency, and current output (Table 7).

Table 5: Association between Age and Sex and the Response Rate

Parameters		Responsive patients (N=56)	Non-responsive patients (N=15)	P-value
		N (%)	N (%)	
Age group	<10	19 (70.4)	8 (29.6)	0.268
	10-19	15 (88.2)	2 (11.8)	
	20-29	10 (71.4)	4 (28.6)	
	≥30	12 (92.3)	1 (7.7)	
Sex	Male	42 (82.4)	9 (17.6)	0.251
	Female	14 (70.0)	6 (30.0)	

Table 6: Association between the Response Rate and Seizure Characteristics

Parameters		Responsive patients (N=56)	Non-responsive patients (N=15)	P-value
		N (%)	N (%)	
Age at onset	< 1 year	19 (70.0)	8 (29.6)	0.364
	1-10 years	29 (85.3)	5 (14.7)	
	>10 years	8 (80.0)	2 (20.0)	
Types of seizure	Focal	10 (76.9)	3 (23.1)	0.370
	Generalized	10 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
	Focal to bilateral tonic-clonic	15 (75.0)	5 (25.0)	
	Multiple types	21 (75.0)	7 (25.0)	
Diagnosis	Lesional	32 (84.2)	6 (15.8)	0.237
	Non-lesional	24 (72.7)	9 (27.3)	
Frequency/month	<20	31 (75.6)	10 (24.4)	0.862
	20-39	10 (83.3)	2 (16.7)	
	40-59	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
	60-79	5 (71.4)	2 (28.6)	
	80-100	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
	>100	56 (85.7)	1 (14.3)	

Table 7: Association between the Response Rate and Treatment

Parameters		Responsive patients (N=56)	Non-responsive patients (N=15)	P-value
		N (%)	N (%)	
Duration of implantation	≤6 months	13 (72.2)	5 (27.8)	0.529
	7-12 months	26 (76.5)	8 (23.5)	
	13-24 months	13 (86.7)	2 (13.3)	
	>24 months	4 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
Pulse width	250 μs	21 (77.8)	6 (22.2)	0.859
	500 μs	35 (79.5)	9 (20.5)	
Signal frequency	20 Hz	5 (83.3)	1 (16.7)	0.341
	25 Hz	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	
	30 Hz	49 (80.3)	12 (19.7)	
Current output	<1 mA	5 (55.6)	4 (44.4)	0.075
	1-<2	13 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
	2-<3 mA	28 (80.0)	7 (20.0)	
	≥3	10 (71.4)	4 (28.6)	

Figure 2: Side Effects of the Treatment. Some Patients Had More than One Side Effect while Others Had No Side Effect

A total of 30 (42.3%) of the patients had one or more side effects. The hoarseness of the voice was the commonest reported side effect (32.4%) followed by shortness of breath (15.5%). As shown in figure 2.

Discussion

Vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) has been widely studied as an adjunctive therapy for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy (DRE), with most reports confirming its effectiveness and acceptable tolerability profile. In the present study, 71 patients with DRE treated at Baghdad Teaching Hospital were reviewed, showing a predominance of male patients (71.8%) and a younger age at implantation, with most patients being younger than 10 years. No significant association was observed between age at implantation and sex, a finding

consistent with previous reports by Elliott et al. and other large series, which similarly failed to demonstrate sex- or age-related differences in response to VNS therapy [12,13]. The overall responder rate in this cohort was 78.9%, which lies within the upper range reported in regional and international studies. Reports from Saudi Arabia and other centers have documented response rates ranging from 50% to 78% [14]. The relatively higher response rate observed in the current study may be partly attributed to the small sample size and variability in follow-up duration. Most patients experienced seizure onset during childhood, particularly between 1 and 10 years of age (47.9%). This finding is in line with epidemiological data suggesting increased vulnerability of the developing brain to epileptogenic insults during early life, including a higher risk of severe seizures and status epilepticus [15]. Analysis according to seizure type showed a heterogeneous distribution, with multiple seizure types being the most frequent. Similar to previous studies, no significant association was found between seizure type and response to VNS [16,17]. The limited sample size likely restricted meaningful subgroup analysis in this regard. Regarding etiology, patients were almost equally divided into lesional and non-lesional groups, with no significant difference in response rate. This finding agrees with earlier studies indicating that etiology alone is not a reliable predictor of VNS outcome, particularly in non-lesional epilepsy where precise mechanisms may be difficult to define [18,19]. Although baseline seizure frequency was not significantly associated with response, a clear post-implantation trend toward reduced seizure burden was observed, with fewer patients experiencing very high seizure frequencies after treatment. Interpretation of seizure frequency, however, was limited by inconsistent documentation, poor compliance in some cases, device-related technical issues, and loss of follow-up during the COVID-19 pandemic. Consistent with prior reports, seizure reduction with VNS appeared to improve gradually over time rather than immediately after implantation [20,21]. Although higher response rates were observed in patients with longer follow-up durations, this association did not reach statistical significance, possibly due to sample size limitations and differences in generator technology between older and newer devices. Stimulation parameters, including output current, frequency, and pulse width, were comparable to those used in other studies [22,23]. No significant association was found between output current and response, supporting previous findings that output current alone is not the primary determinant of efficacy [24]. Side effects were common but generally mild and transient, with hoarseness of voice and dyspnea being the most frequent, consistent with published literature [25,26].

These effects were effectively managed through parameter adjustments, and serious complications were rare. Overall, the findings support VNS as a safe and effective long-term treatment option for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy, while highlighting the need for larger, prospective, multicenter studies with standardized documentation and follow-up to better define predictors of response and optimize patient management.

Conclusion

VNS as adjuvants treatment in drug resistant epilepsy and in patients who not a candidate for respective surgery. Which is save and well tolerated treatment for adults and children. And the stimulation efficacy increases over time.

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